

ISic0792

I.Sicily inscription 0792

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Foundations of teatro Vittorio Emanuele (24 Nov 1899)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3555

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus) s(acrum)
2. Carpioni fil(io) dul
3. cissimo Carpion pater
4. abreptumabrepto sibi fato qui
5. vixit incomparabilis
6. ulli an(nis) XX

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 with photograph

Translation (en)

Sacred to the shades of the underworld. Carpio as father (set this up) for Carpio, his sweetest son, snatched from him by fate, who lived unequalled by anyone for twenty years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175728

EDR 076853

EDCS 9300940

PHI 313669

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1977.0329

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 37

Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica.* 3: 252-270. At 254 no.4

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0792. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4339106>